

Wireless IMU- and EMG-sensors for controlled Functional Electrical Stimulation

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Abstract—This contribution describes wireless IMU- and EMG-sensors for the control of Functional Electrical Stimulation that have been developed within the European project RETRAINER. Combined IMU- and EMG-sensors shall be integrated into the RETRAINER exoskeleton (S1 system) for estimation of the arm posture and for EMG-triggered stimulation. IMU-sensors shall be used within the RETRAINER hand neuroprosthesis (S2 system) to estimate the finger and hand motion. Both sensor types are Bluetooth 5 ready and incorporate a powerful Cortex M4F processor. Data preprocessing, like orientation estimation and adaptive linear prediction EMG filtering for estimating residual volitional muscle activity, can be implemented directly on the wireless sensors. This reduces the data rate significantly down to the stimulation frequency.

I. INTRODUCTION

The combined use of Functional Electrical Stimulation (FES) and robotics is advocated to improve rehabilitation outcomes after stroke. Therefore, a hybrid arm rehabilitation system, called RETRAINER S1, has been developed within the European project RETRAINER that combines both technologies [1]. Additionally, a hand rehabilitation system, called RETRAINER S2 has been built, that can be used separately from S1 [3].

The arm rehabilitation system consists of a passive 4-degrees-of-freedom exoskeleton equipped with springs to provide gravity compensation and electromagnetic brakes to hold target positions. An EMG-triggered stimulation controller is included in the RETRAINER S1 system. Up to two arm muscles can be stimulated simultaneously. For each muscle, the residual volitional EMG signal is detected by means of an adaptive linear prediction filter [2] and used to trigger the onset of a predetermined stimulation sequence applied to the same muscle. Once the system automatically recognizes that the target is reached, the brakes are activated, and the stimulation is switched off. During the stimulation phase, the volitional EMG signal is continuously monitored in order to provide a visual feedback about the patient's volitional involvement at the end of the execution of each task. The arm motion is currently assessed by means of encoders at the exoskeleton's joints for monitoring the progress of therapy, e.g., via the achieved range of motion.

The S2 hand rehabilitation system consists of an array electrode in combination with a wrist/hand orthosis with

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Fig. 1. PCB 3D export of the built IMU/EMG sensor (left) and IMU sensor (right) with dimensions.

integrated wired IMU sensors [3].

At the current state, the EMG sensor of the S1 arm rehabilitation device as well as the IMU sensors of the S2 system are connected via wires to an ARM Linux-based embedded control system (ECS). The raw data are sent at 100Hz (IMU) and 4kHz (EMG) with full resolution to the control system where the preprocessing and the control strategy is executed. The developed wireless sensors firstly aim at an improved usability and flexibility of the system by reducing the amount of required cabling and weight of the systems. Furthermore, the estimation of the arm posture shall be enhanced by the integration of combined IMU- and EMG-sensors into S1. The sensors must run all signal processing on board to allow a reliable, real-time capable data exchange at the stimulation frequency with Bluetooth low-energy.

II. METHODS

One combined IMU/EMG sensor and one pure IMU sensor have been developed. The PCB of the two sensor types and the dimensions are shown in Fig. 1. Both sensors are using the FCC certified module BMD-300 by Rigado (USA). The module combines a Bluetooth 5 compliant 2.4 GHz transceiver with an ARM Cortex M4F CPU. Due to the powerful CPU the preprocessing of the raw sensor data, i.e. orientation estimation and the adaptive linear prediction filtering of the volitional muscle activity, can be executed directly on the sensors. The block diagram of the IMU/EMG sensor is displayed in Fig. 2. Both sensors employ the IMU module BMX055 by Bosch (Germany).

The applied method for orientation estimation is displayed in Fig. 3. We implemented the orientation estimation algorithm from [4] directly in the interrupt routine of both sensors. Hence, it is possible to run the strap-down integration

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the IMU/EMG sensor. The pure IMU sensor does not contain the analog front-end, filter and protection circuits, and has a reduced power module.

Fig. 3. Orientation estimation algorithm according to [4] with increased sampling frequency for the strap-down integration.

of the angular rate at 1000Hz which increases the accuracy. The resulting orientation estimate can be transferred as a quaternion or Euler angles to the controller. The angles will then be used within RETRAINER S1 and S2 to estimate joint angles of the human arm and hand, respectively.

The IMU/EMG sensor possesses an input filter and a protection circuit which makes it possible to measure the EMG signals while stimulation is applied to the same muscle up to a stimulation voltage of 150 V. The analog front-end ADS1292 by Texas Instruments (USA) is used which incorporates active shielding, common mode rejection via a reference electrode driver and a resolution of 24 bit at up to 8kHz. To store raw data for calibration routines an external RAM is integrated with 1 MB. Galvanic isolation is guaranteed via a battery which can be only charged if no electrode cable is connected.

Both sensors are powered with a small Lithium polymer battery which allows an operation of up to 8 hours.

III. PRELIMINARY EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

With the first manufactured prototypes of the IMU/EMG and IMU sensors, several experiments have been executed with healthy subjects. In Fig. 4 (a) and (b) the measured volitional EMG activity at the wrist extensor of one healthy subject and the resulting M-wave (FES-evoked EMG-response) for different stimulation intensities also at the wrist extensor

Fig. 4. (a) Volitional EMG measurement of healthy subject at 2 kHz at the wrist extensor. (b) M-wave at different stimulation intensities at the wrist extensor. (c) Obtained Euler angles for the IMU sensor resting on a table.

are shown, respectively. The resulting signal-to-noise ratio is sufficient to detect the onset of a volitional movement. Furthermore, Fig. 4 (c) shows the low drift of the IMU sensor orientation. Here the sensor was resting on the table and the orientation was estimated with the algorithm described in [4] without using the magnetometer information (advisable for indoor measurements). The maximum drift of the resulting Euler angles is less than $2.5^\circ/\text{min}$.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The sensors are ready for integration into S1 and S2 using a customized Bluetooth dongle with a Rigado module at the embedded control system. Only final EMC tests need to be performed before using the sensors inside clinical environments. A study with healthy subjects is planned to compare the EMG signal processing for the wireless and cable-based solutions. Afterward, exploratory trials with stroke patients will be performed to assess the entire functionality of the wireless sensor system.

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